

Skills Needs in Ethiopia: Insights from Three Industries

Skills for Industry Policy Brief Ethiopia #1 (2020)

At a glance

This policy brief presents findings from a survey conducted with 165 manufacturing companies, as the first stage of the “Skills-for-Industry” - project. The project inquires into the contribution of vocational skills development to industrial transformation and inclusive growth. The brief mainly examines the availability of skills at lower and higher occupational levels, and assesses how skills shortages impact the operations, growth and transformation of companies across various manufacturing industries.

Background

Ethiopia's economy is among the fastest growing economies in the developing world. Over the last two decades, Ethiopia has achieved two-digit gross domestic product growth in real terms (MOI, September 2013). In order to sustain its growth trajectory, the Ethiopian government developed successive Growth and Transformation Plans (GTP-I, II and III, 2010-2025), which aimed to move away from an agriculture-led growth path to a model of competitive manufacturing industries that would turn Ethiopia into a middle income country by 2025. The GTP recognises that human resource development plays a vital role, affirming that a skilled workforce is crucial to achieving sustainable economic growth and competitiveness in manufacturing. Vocational skills development (VSD) programmes are key to strengthening the skills of technical graduates. These skills have the potential to contribute to the growth and transformation of the manufacturing sector. Realising this foundation, the government launched ambitious reforms of higher education and technical and vocational education and

training (TVET), with the objective of producing competent and qualified skilled employees who would meet industry's skill needs. However, the country's TVET system struggles to produce quality trained graduates that meet industry needs. Addressing this issue is key, in order to create more and better paying jobs and improve Ethiopia's competitiveness.

Methodology

A regional survey of 165 manufacturing companies in Oromia, Tigray and Addis Ababa was conducted, of which 65 companies were in the textile and garment industry, 67 were in metalworks, and 33 were in the leather and shoe industry. The survey collected information on companies' low and high skills level workers, existing training activities and factors contributing to the companies' growth and transformation.

Availability of employees and companies' skills requirement

Even though some companies reported that they encountered some difficulties in recruiting highly skilled workers compared to low skilled workers, the majority of the companies surveyed – around 70% – reported that they did not experience difficulties in recruiting general workers, supervisors and higher management employees from the labour market, as is indicated in figure 1.

The analysis of the survey findings from the three industries (figure 1) shows that 23.4% of firms in garments and textiles, 28.9% in metals and 40.6% in leather faced difficulties in finding operators; respectively, 34.4% of companies in textiles and garments, 38.7 % in metals and 50% in leather and shoes found it difficult to recruit skilled technicians. Additionally,

around 30 % of companies in the metal, and leather and shoe industries struggled to find adequate supervisors and higher management employees.

negatively. Nevertheless, it is important to understand that skills shortages at the level of supervisors and higher management, while lower in absolute terms, show similar patterns.

Skills development and industrial growth

The survey revealed that a considerable number of companies have grown, despite the shortages at different skill levels. Figure 3 illustrates skills shortages with respect to operators and technicians, and their occurrence in companies, which have grown/not grown during the past five years.

The effect of skills shortages on business operations is illustrated in figure 2. The survey indicates that a significant number – more than 80% – of the companies that reported difficulties in finding skilled workers in the labour market concluded that this skills shortage had negative effects on their business operations.

To be precise, the analysis of the survey findings from the three sectors, in figure 2, shows that 86.7% of the textile and garment companies, 90% of metal companies and 92.3% of leather and shoe companies found the shortage of skilled operators significantly affected their business operations.

The skills shortages with respect to operators and technicians seem to have had an effect on the growth of the leather and shoe companies, compared to the other two industries. 50% of leather and shoe companies that have not grown report skills shortages at the operator and technician level. Interestingly, for companies operating in the garment sector, the trend was reversed: the companies which have grown had a harder time finding skilled employees. Also, figure 3 indicates that 25% of the metal companies that have not grown have experienced skills shortages at the operator level, whilst 39% have experienced skills shortages at the technician level. For the metal industry, there were no significant differences between companies that have grown and those that have not.

In the same manner, 86.4% of the textile and garment, 88.5% of the metal and 93.3% of the leather and shoe companies in that group stated that the shortage of skilled technicians affected their business operations

As illustrated in figure 3, 27% of companies in the textile and garment industry, 56% of the companies in the leather and shoe industry and 39% of the companies in the metal industries that have not grown, have experienced skills shortages in terms of techni-

cal staff. On the other hand, 15% of companies in the textile and garment industry, 50% of the companies in the leather and shoe industry and 25% of the companies in the metal industries that have not grown have experienced skills shortages in terms of operators.

Skill development and industrial transformation

The skills shortages with respect to operators and technicians and their potential effect on the transformation of the surveyed companies is shown in figure 4.

Fig 4: Experienced skills shortages by transformation

This graph shows that a considerable number of companies – in the metal, and leather and shoe industry –, which have not transformed, have also experienced skills shortages at the operator and technician levels. Moreover, figure 4 demonstrates that of the companies that have transformed in the textile and garment industry, leather and shoe industry, and metal industry, 18%, 33% and 42% have experienced skills shortages at the technician level, respectively, and 9%, 33% and 25% have experienced skills shortages at the operator level, respectively. Consequently,

it can be inferred that for the garment and leather companies, which have become more complex, it was more difficult to find skilled operators. This does not hold true for technicians, however.

Summary of key findings

- The majority of the companies indicated that they had no difficulty finding employees at the general worker, supervisor and higher management levels, but some difficulties finding employees at the technician and operator levels. The companies which did experience difficulties in finding operators and technicians stated that these difficulties significantly affected their business operations.
- The skills shortages at the operator and technician levels have significantly affected the growth of the leather and shoe companies, compared to the textile and garment, and metal ones. On the other hand, regardless of shortages of operators and technicians, company growth in the metal industry does not appear to be linked to skills shortages (compared to the textile and garment, and leather and shoe industries).
- For garment companies, a relationship between skills shortages and growth and transformation seems to exist: Companies that have grown and/or transformed have experienced a higher degree of skills shortages.

References & Data

- Own survey
- Ethiopian Industrial Development Strategic Plan (2013-2025) FDRE Ministry of Industry September 2013 Addis Ababa

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